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SEXOPATHOLOGY - A CRIME COMMITTED IN THE SEXUAL SPHERE

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Abstract. The 20th century saw the birth of three strong and pervasive ideologies: fascism, communism, and liberalism. Fascism and communism were lost in the debris of history in the 20th century. As for liberalism, it is now flourishing and flourishing. I do not want to present the 21st century or the age of liberalism only in dark colors. Good things are happening, but I'd rather talk about the vices, because they are very noticeable for such a small, traditional, Christian-Puritan country like Georgia.

Keywords: Sexopathology, liberalism, sexual crime.

სექსოპათოლოგია - სექსუალურ სფეროში ჩადენილი დანაშაული

მაია კერკენჯია

ასოცირებული პროფესორი, საქართველოს ფიზიკური აღზრდისა და სპორტის სახელმწიფო სასწავლო უნივერსიტეტი;

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აბსტრაქტი. მე-20 საუკუნეში დაიბადა სამი მყარი და ყოვლისმომცველი იდეოლოგია: ფაშიზმი, კომუნიზმი და ლიბერალიზმი. ფაშიზმი და კომუნიზმი მე-20 საუკუნეშივე ჩაიკარგა ისტორიის ნამსხვრევებში. რაც შეეხება ლიბერალიზმს, ახლა ყვავის და იფურჩქნება. 21-ე საუკუნე ანუ ლიბერალიზმის ეპოქა არ მსურს მხოლოდ მუქ ფერებში წარმოვაჩინო. კარგიც ხდება, თუმცა ჯობს მანკიერებებზე ვისაუბრო, რადგან მეტად ყურადსაღებია ისეთი პატარა, ტრადიციული, ქრისტიანულ-პურიტანული ქვეყნისთვის, როგორც საქართველოა.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: სექსოპათოლოგია, ლიბერალიზმი, სექსუალური დანაშაული.

Introduction

I, who used to work in the field of forensic medical examination, have often come across crimes committed in the sexual sphere and helped the court to identify the culprit, while there was no suitable special technology, database in social networks, and we identified a dangerous criminal only by evidence and intuition.

Before moving directly to subject of crime, let's first distinguish sexopathology from crime. Because in the era of liberalization of the 21st century, many things were reevaluated and a conglomerate of pathology-crimes was created, that is, crime was recognized as a norm, which in turn greatly increased the list of crimes. All of this is backed by the statistics of crimes committed in the sexual sphere, which can be freely searched on the Internet and is transparent for all interested persons.

Issues

Let's start with the disease or pathology. Such is hermaphroditism, both true and false, that is, psychological. In the first case, the subject has characteristics of both sexes, while in case of

false hermaphroditism, the subject's problem is only in his perception. That is, he feels like a person of the opposite sex. He dresses and behaves like one. Both of these cases are considered as a pathology, I emphasize it as a pathology and not as a norm, let alone a crime. Although this is not a crime, the practice of advertising it, which we see in the conditions of liberalization, is a crime, moreover - reprehensible.

Another issue is pedophilia and rape - both of these are the most serious crimes punishable under Article 137 of the Georgian legislation. Rape is an abusive sexual relationship. It can be done by using force, or by psychological influence (threats, blackmail, helplessness).

It is easy for a forensic expert to determine rape by physical force, because there are signs of violence visible clearly. In the case of psychological impact, it is necessary to involve a psychologist, because the medical expert is powerless here. I hasten to point out that pedophilia is punishable even if it occurred with the consent and desire of the "victim". I will refrain from going into more depth, because it is no longer within the competence of a forensic medical expert.

Research Results

Now, let's move on to the main thing, which is considered normal for a liberal society and completely unacceptable for a healthy one. It is the satisfaction of sexual needs in an unnatural way. This is homosexuality in women (Sapphism) and homosexuality in men. This act, although to our surprise it was not punished in ancient Rome and Greece, was later recognized as a crime in Europe and became punishable by hanging and burning at the stake, and in Asia by stoning and premature burial. In our era, since liberalization has recognized it as a norm, its determination from a purely medical point of view is absolutely useless and unnecessary.

Discussion

I just want to point out that humans were created by God as a man and as a woman, and awareness of this is utmost necessary, and going against nature with surgical intervention and hormone therapy causes important physiological and psychological changes in the body and is not safe from a purely medical point of view. Psychological change is often a prerequisite for committing atrocious crimes, which we can look up on the Internet.

The stressful condition of such people is indicated by how they clothe and behave, ignorance of public opinion, nihilistic attitude and depression, which is often disguised by aggression towards others. Unfortunately, today's news media outlets try to justify their behavior.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to express that a lifestyle inconsistent with our values is unacceptable for the Georgian people. Additionally, the extensive propaganda promoting such lifestyles is concerning.

It is reassuring to note that a bill addressing these issues has been proposed in Parliament. With due respect, I would like to emphasize the importance of preserving our traditions and considering the future of our children. Our history and unblemished past are significant, extending back millennia.

References:

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